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JAMES M. NORTHINGTON, M.D., Editor

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Massive Doses of Vitamin C and the Virus Diseases

F. R. KLENNER, M.D., Reidsville, North Carolina

IT has been reported that one of the mold-derived drugs, in addition to being a good antibiotic, is a super-vitamin. Conversely, we argue that vitamin C, besides being an essential vitamin, is a super-antibiotic. Vitamin C in vitro, if maintained at body temperature, inactivates certain toxins at an unbelievable rate. Five parts per thousand of vitamin C with toxins and appropriate controls, incubated at 37° C. for 48 hours showed when tested on mice the minimal lethal dose for the control tubes to be 1/16,000 c.c., while that from the mixture of vitamin C and toxin was only 1/1,000 of a c.c. (Klegler, Guggenheim, Warburg, 1938). In this study the loss of vitamin C in toxin broth and ordinary broth controls followed a constant pattern; the loss, however, was always greater in the toxin broth tube. The difference between the rate of disappearance of vitamin C in toxin and ordinary broth was more striking the greater the concentration of vitamin C. It is, therefore, reasonable to conclude that the degree of neutralization in a virus infection will be in proportion to the concentration of the vitamin and the length of time in which it is employed.

Since it has long been known that the virus organism resembles more the toxins and ferments than the common animate causes of disease, it would seem plausible that the detoxication effected

by vitamin C is produced by a direct combination of the vitamin with the toxin and/or virus, this followed by the oxidation of the new compound which destroys both the virus and/or toxin and the vitamin. This destruction of the virus by oxidation has been concurred in by many investigators. Since vitamin C is an integral part of the oxidation-reduction system of the body, its function in the role of an antibiotic becomes intelligible. To appreciate the antagonistic properties of vitamin C against the virus organism and the chemical ferments of exotoxin-producing microorganisms, one must forget its present academic status as a factor essential for life. A cow is valuable to the farmer not only for her ability to produce milk, but also as a source of organic fertilizer. Vitamin C, likewise, is important, not only as a detoxifying agent, as a catalyst aiding cellular respiration by acting as a hydrogen transport, as a catalyst in the assimilation of iron, and as a conservator of collagen fibers and bundles in tissues of mesenchymal origin; but, also, because of its function as a reducing agent or the precursor of such a substance. In this latter capacity it fulfills the requirements of an antibiotic. A striking phenomenon of vitamin C is the similarity of response, whether to correct pathologic processes due to a deficiency of this compound, acting as a vitamin; or to destroy the ferments of microorganisms, acting as an antibiotic.

Within a few hours after institution of adequate vitamin C therapy to correct an avitaminosis, his-

sulfate as a compress gave prompt relief of the pain and swelling. In two of these cases fluctuation ensued and healing was effected by surgical drainage and the application of compresses. The impression in these two cases was that a vein had been opened by the needle. The exudate was dark and both the slide and culture studies were negative for bacteria. 3) Endothelial irritation in three cases. Acute pain radiated from the site of the injection to the shoulder. In each instance the concentration of the vitamin was one gram to each 5 c.c. solution and the amount given exceeded two grams. After slowing the rate of injection this reaction did not occur. 4) Venous thrombosis in one case. The concentration was 500 mg. per c.c. solution; the total dose 5 c.c. Compressing relieved the pain. The pathology was very similar to that following the use of 50 per cent dextrose solution. 5) Syncope—In maximum doses given IV a sensation of fainting and dyspnea occurred seven times. Five of these patients were over 55 years of age. The disagreeable symptoms were relieved by slowing the speed of the injections. 6) Rash—In three cases a pin-point dermatitis occurred, limited to the face and upper third of the torso, identical to that seen in infants taking orange juice. This did not necessitate discontinuance of therapy and cleared spontaneously several days after vitamin C was stopped.

Calcium, *in vivo*, duplicates the chemical behavior of vitamin C in many respects. Calcium gluconate and calcium lextrinate were used in conjunction with vitamin C therapy in a small series of pulmonary virus infections and in mild cases of influenza. There was a definite synergistic response. Patients with colds derived most benefit from this combined treatment. Because of its action on cardiac muscle, the use of calcium was limited to adults and the amount injected to two grams per day. One gram administered IV at moderate speed will so slow the heart as in many cases to produce syncope. If the concentration becomes great enough cardiac arrest in a tonically contracted state might result. It is, however, quite possible that, with the proper ionic balance of calcium and vitamin C in the same solution, larger amounts could be given without side effects. The massive dose schedule limits the usefulness of the calcium ion in virus diseases to that of an adjuvant only.

In all of the cases of virus infection reviewed in this study one laboratory finding stood out as of great significance. On admission to the hospital the first routine urine examination showed some degree of glycosuria. The pattern of the qualitative Benedict's reaction was constant enough to postulate that the higher the reading the more severe was the pathology. Repeat urine sugar studies following vitamin C therapy revealed complete clearing. This was true even though fruit juices were forced to tolerance. This finding confirmed the

knowledge that interference with the normal physiology of the adrenal glands, either by the toxins produced by microorganisms or by surgery, has a profound influence on metabolism, especially of the carbohydrates. Adrenalin in the blood stream causes hyperglycemia with resulting glycosuria. Adrenalin acts either by stimulation of the sympathetic nervous system or directly via the blood. This action of adrenalin is via the blood only, because the effect, as demonstrated in experimental animals, is still realized after destruction of the cord and sympathetic plexuses and degeneration of the peripheral post-ganglionic fibers (Evans, 1930). The glycosuria found in these cases was not due to a lowering of the threshold for sugar excretion by the kidney, paralleling a phloridzin diabetes, since the carbohydrate mechanism was associated with a hyperglycemia (Zuelzer, 1901, Metzger, 1902, Paton, 1903). Likewise there was no evidence of kidney damage. Albumin was reported negative and the microscopic examination showed no cells or casts. Apparently this is a condition of artificial diabetes mellitus, which would suggest the answer for the diabetic who loses ability to maintain sugar-insulin balance when embarrassed with an acute infection.

The story of a 7-year-old boy may have a lesson. He has been known to be diabetic since the age of four years. Any incident of infection in this lad produced an alarming interference of his sugar-insulin-diet equilibrium. Recently he contracted measles, and as the disease process developed toward its height the urine sugar curve swung sharply upward. From an occasional dose of 5 units regular insulin his requirement rose to 30 units regular insulin, three times each day, while still running a 3- or 4-plus Benedict's test. (Other forms of insulin proved by trial to be too dangerous.) At the peak of his infection vitamin C was started in a modifying dose of one gram every four hours. His general condition soon improved and in the course of several days he returned to his usual diet-insulin schedule and his usual urine sugar. In patients with diabetes, vitamin C should be discontinued just as soon as the temperature returns to normal. Prolonged use of vitamin C might prove undesirable due to its dehydrating and diuretic powers.

The pathologic process at work here is only compatible with abnormal amounts of adrenalin in the blood stream. It is not a response to an emotional stimulus to the adrenal medulla, since free adrenalin in the circulating blood has a transitory action, being so rapidly oxidized that none gets into the urine. This suggested that the regulator of the adrenalin mechanism had been removed, so that a constant supply of adrenalin would be present in the blood, making possible a concentration sufficiently high to cause constant vasoconstriction.

Ritzmann (1909) found that adrenalin affected carbohydrate metabolism only when this vasoconstriction phase existed. This finding was concurred in by Lusk (1914), who further concluded that this action on blood vessels caused asphyxia of the tissues which tended to increase the acidity of the blood and the tissues. This superimposed acidity further promotes the production of adrenalin hyperglycemia (Peters and Geyelin, 1917). McDannell and Underhill (1919), studying these phenomena in rabbits, found that slight hyperglycemia could be controlled by the administration of sodium carbonate.

The rationale of forcing fruit juices in the old treatment of colds was based on this theory as postulated by Hawley et al. (1936) that a highly alkaline urine would have lower amounts of vitamin C than a highly acid urine; the alkaline ash from the organic acids serving to retain the vitamin C in the blood and tissues where Nature had assigned it to guard against the many enemies of the body—the toxins and ferments of bacteria. As a result of avitaminosis C, liver glycogen is mobilized—glycogenolysis; and further storing of sugar in the liver is prevented—glycogenesis (Mackenzie, 1917). To further enhance the hyperglycemia this vasoconstriction brings about a decrease in the pancreatic secretions by lessening the amount of blood passing through the gland (Mann and McLachlan, 1917).

That the adrenal glands and vitamin C are closely allied in the defense of the body has been proven by experimentation and by autopsy. In normal persons any excess of vitamin C is excreted in the urine. In persons suffering with an acute infection, particularly a virus infection, vitamin C is not only absent from the urine but is also missing from the blood serum. This is true even when moderate amounts are given intravenously. These observations on serum were made with a Klett-Summerson photoelectric colorimeter using the method described by Mindlin and Butler. The observations on the urine were conducted according to the instructions of Goldsmith and Ellenger. Harde and Benjamin (1934-35) found the vitamin C fraction of the adrenal glands greatly reduced in monkeys killed or paralyzed by the virus of poliomyelitis. Yavorsky, Almoden and King (1934) reported identical findings in humans having died of various infectious agents.

This gives us an important concept of the value of vitamin C in virus diseases. The explanation for the absence of vitamin C in the infectious states is that this agent joins with the toxin and/or virus to form a new compound which is then destroyed by oxidation. Since the body is dependent on food for vitamin C to meet its daily needs, it is obvious that the body tissues would soon be depleted, and we would expect to find evidence of a prescor-

butic state in patients who had hypovitaminosis C. In patients seriously ill with a virus invader, the added strain on the capillaries by the application of a tourniquet, even for a few seconds, produced petechial hemorrhages at the site of constriction. Since not all patients thus demonstrated this capillary weakness, all patients ill with a virus infection were investigated by the aid of a petechiometer. Increased capillary fragility was found to exist in all cases, and the number of petechiae as expressed in centimeters of mercury followed the urine sugar findings. This deficiency syndrome was reversed as the glycosuria cleared, indicating that both were responsive to a proper plasma level for vitamin C.

At this same time the anaerobic conditions in the tissues will be relieved by the catalytic action of vitamin C acting as a gas transport to aid this cellular respiration. The abnormal acidity of the blood and tissues will be removed and abnormal amounts of free adrenalin will disappear from the blood stream. Following this the constriction of the blood vessels will cease, allowing the liver and pancreatic tissue to return to normal function. Continuance of frequent injections of properly calculated doses of vitamin C will restore the normal physiology of the body. This is not all of the story.

Lojkin (1937), studying the various phases of the inactivation of crystalline tobacco mosaic virus by l-ascorbic acid, suggested that the action was not due to reduced vitamin C nor to the irreversibly oxidized dehydroascorbic acid. Lojkin felt that it was due to a specific intermediate product which is formed in the course of the catalytic auto-oxidation of vitamin C, an action stimulated by the presence of copper ions. This intermediate product must be a peroxide because a peroxide is formed during copper-catalyzed oxidation of vitamin C. This peroxide is decomposed as rapidly as it is formed (Barrow, De Meio, Klemperer, 1935-36). Lyman and associates (1937) confirmed the peroxide theory by observing that the oxygen uptake, beyond that calculated for the reaction ascorbic acid to dehydroascorbic acid, was not due to further oxidation of dehydroascorbic acid to an irreversible oxidation product, because treatment of the oxidized solution with hydrogen sulfide gave complete recovery of the ascorbic acid. These men also found that copper catalysis accelerates not only the reversible oxidation of vitamin C, but also further oxidation of dehydroascorbic acid. This action of the copper ion elucidates the findings that vitamin C in massive, frequent doses works better in the body than in a laboratory test tube.

Hippocrates declared the highest duty of medicine to be to get the patient well. He further declared that, of several remedies physicians should choose the least sensational. Vitamin C would seem to meet both these requirements.